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Obstacles for Women Entrepreneurs in Bangladesh

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Abstract: Studies on women entrepreneurship have witnessed a rapid growth over the past 30 years. The field is in an adolescence stage with a considerable number of journal articles, literature reviews and books being published on women entrepreneurs. The objective of this study is two fold. First is to examine the number of papers published on women entrepreneurship in 12 established entrepreneurship journals from 1900 to 2016. Second is to assess the growth of the field by specifically reviewing literature reviews published from 1980s till 2016 and put forward future research directions. Our review findings suggest that there is still a long way to go in terms of building a strong theoretical base for research on women entrepreneurship. The lens of feminist theories can be applied in conjunction with the existing entrepreneurship theories to advance the field. Methodologically, past research is dominated by the positivist paradigm and there is a need to embrace innovative methods to build explanations using a constructionist approach. Further, studies are mostly restricted within national boundaries primarily being conducted in developed economies. There is a need to build transnational networks and foster professional communities to enable the growth of the field.

Keywords: Women Entrepreneurs, Bangladesh

1. Introduction

Apart from the access to finance, other factors at the individual, the household, and the local level also contribute to the entrepreneurship development of women (Chowdhury, 2011). Age of an individual influences his or her decision to become an entrepreneur (Lin et al. 2000; Block and Sandner 2009; Haapanen and Tervo 2009). The relationship between age and the decision of an individual to start a business is not linear. In this aspect, Taylor (2004), Block and Sandner (2009), and Haapanen and Tervo (2009) find a negative non-linear relationship between age and the decision of a person to become an entrepreneur. Similarly, Miller (1984) finds a concave relationship between the self-employment decision and age with the highest impact of the age range of 35-44 on the self-employment decision of individuals. In contrast, Yang et al. (2008) do not find age as a significant determinant for nascent entrepreneurship. Education might influence entrepreneurial decision of individuals in many ways. Education is likely to have a positive influence on the propensity to become self-employed as it

contributes to the enhancement of managerial ability of individuals (Calvo and Wellisz 1980). In contrast, education is likely to influence the propensity to become self-employed negatively as it generates better employment options than self-employment for individuals and thus, increases the opportunity cost of becoming self-employed (van der Sluis et al 2005). The probability of starting a business has a gender dimension. Women are less likely to be self-employed and more likely to exit self-employment compared to men (Lin et al. 2000; Demircuc-Kunt et al. 2009). In contrast, Yang et al. (2008) do not find gender as an important determinant of entrepreneurship. After reviewing some literature on minorities and self-employment in the United Kingdom, Borooah and Hart (1999) express that minorities are discriminated in the labor market. Lofstrom and Wang (2006) and Fertala (2008) find that foreigners are less likely to survive in self-employment. Audretsch et al. (2007) also find that religious minorities, such as Muslims and Christians, in India are likely to become entrepreneurs compared to religious majority Hindus. Regarding the influence of the number of household members, especially the number of children, on the entrepreneurial decision, the available evidences is mixed (Borjas 1986; Lin et al. 2000; Fairlie 1999; Demircuc-Kunt et al. (2009); Block and Sandner 2009; Haapanen and Tervo 2009). Some argue that more household members absorb more household resources and time which increase the likelihood of the failure of existing businesses and reduce the likelihood of starting new businesses. On the other hand, some argue that more household members indicate the availability of a higher amount of cheap labor supply which in turn increases the likelihood of starting a business and the success in existing businesses. The presence of another earner or more earners in the household helps that household to start a business (Borooah and Hart 1999). It is expected that the ownership and the size of assets have positive impacts on the entrepreneurial decision of households as assets provide the required startup capital for new enterprises, provide additional capital for existing businesses, and help entrepreneurs to get loans when assets are required to offer as collateral (Paulson and Townsend 2001). Lu and Tao (2010) find the home ownership as an important determinant of the entrepreneurial decision of individuals in China. Bruderl et al. (1998) conclude that a higher amount of capital reduces the likelihood of business failure. However, Millan et al. 2012 assert that the econometric estimation of impacts of assets on the entrepreneurial decision of individuals is difficult due to the endogeneity problem. An access to finance has been recognized as one of positive determinants of entrepreneurship as it helps potential entrepreneurs to acquire the amount of capital that is required for starting a business. The credit constraint has a gender characteristic (Arenius and Minniti 2005). Apart from the above mentioned factors, other factors, like infrastructure, opportunity cost, also contribute to the entrepreneurial decision of individuals. On the basis of the review of the literature, Yu and Stough (2006) assert that closeness to market and business infrastructure contributes to the development of entrepreneurial activities. Chowdhury (2011) asserts that the armed conflict has a negative impact on entrepreneurship.

Engaging ladies in Bangladesh are extremely intense because of such male overwhelmed society; yet it isn't outlandish. The improvement and contribution of ladies in social and business field in step by step expanding. Many NGO's and Development associations are working for the ladies. Presently a-days, ladies are conquering numerous social issues with the assistance of numerous improvement associations. In the South Asia, the advancement of

ladies strengthening is noteworthy. Ladies are presently assuming many significant jobs in various parts with progress. In Bangladesh, there are numerous instances of its prosperity. Presently, there is no zone or part in Bangladesh where ladies are absent. From business to the pioneer, ladies are all over the place. Bangladesh is frequently referred to as a worldwide model for manageable monetary advancement. Notwithstanding being one of the world's biggest as far as populace, and most inclined to cataclysmic events because of worldwide environmental change, the nation has kept up a great 6% in addition to yearly monetary development direction amid the previous decade. Likewise worth thought is the way that Bangladesh's monetary ascent has been consistent regardless of its dubious progress towards a stable fair framework and the grim worldwide financial atmosphere. The legislature has been complimented worldwide for improving the lives of poor people, and especially ladies. It has been perceived by the UN as being one of only a handful couple of nations that is on track and has made "amazing advancement" towards gathering its Millennium Development Goals by 2015. As indicated by various reports, the nation's attention on giving ladies better wellbeing and increasingly financial self-sufficiency has significantly affected rustic family unit salaries, destitution decrease and expanded instructive enrolment, especially for females who for the most part linger behind guys in the Global South. The Economist (Nov 3, 2012) takes note of that "both the blast in the material business and the landing of microcredit have, in the course of recent years, place cash into ladies' pockets—from which it is bound to be spent on wellbeing, training and better sustenance." The material business in Bangladesh, viewed as the way to its monetary development, utilizes almost 4 million individuals, a large portion of whom are ladies. There is a bounty of writing supporting the connection between ladies' strengthening in the financial part in Bangladesh and the nation's supported monetary improvement direction. Since the 1980s, a momentous change has been in progress in Bangladesh. When the scene of ceaseless starvation, the nation is currently sustenance independent, and its economy has found the middle value of around 6 percent development in later a long time (Schleifer and Nakagaki, 2014). Simultaneously, a blasting, send out arranged article of clothing part has created work open doors for urban ladies, and microfinance has risen as an approach to channel advances to provincial business visionaries (Schleifer and Nakagaki, 2014). Women-possessed organizations have moved toward becoming drivers of ladies' monetary strengthening. They have been pioneers in a dynamic administration division, which obliges new gatherings of shoppers. Ladies alumni of Bangladesh's colleges have put their abilities and information to rehearse in the business world. Further, an enormous craftsmanship segment has developed, with little ladies claimed firms selling highquality merchandise and coordinating into supply chains of global brands

Theoretical discussion As per GEM (2011) and Khan (2004), the individual examinations on female business are divided what's more, disconnected and depict just little sections of the female enterprising populace. The hypothetical instruments created in different territories are every now and again connected that are feeble in legitimacy and unwavering quality. Cooper's (1991) system recognizes three gatherings of impacts that influence the start-up and development of new pursuit: predecessor impacts (for example the foundation factors, for example, family impact and hereditary elements that influence inspiration, aptitudes and information), hatchery experience (for example the idea of association that the business visionary was utilized in just before beginning another endeavor the aptitudes realized there),

and natural variables (for example monetary conditions, access to investment and bolster administrations, good examples and so forth.

Methodology

This part of our research describes the methods used for data collection it also defines the sample size and population used for collecting data.

Research Strategy

The research questions we used for this study were exploratory in nature. This paper has the aim of getting insights of the phenomena of experience or challenges faced by women entrepreneurs in Bangladesh. There are few researchers who have worked in the field of entrepreneurship in Bangladesh, similarly, the context of women entrepreneurship is unable to get attention for the study, especially in Bangladesh. Therefore, this research paper discovers the issues which have not been discussed before in Bangladeshi context. To get a detailed understanding of why women want to become entrepreneurs and what are the social and cultural effects we conducted open-ended interviews. The research method that we chose to use was qualitative research to get detail and in-depth information by interviews because we want to explore the insights of the issue. As Bryman and Bell (2011) suggested that quantitative method produce numerical data, on the other hand, qualitative research method caters to explanatory data. On qualitative research method, Neergaard and Ulhøi (2006) argue that qualitative research method is more suitable to understand the phenomenon of the entrepreneurship because it gives the in-depth analysis of the phenomenon and is more detailed based. Bryman and Bell (2011) revealed their distress over the subjectivity of the qualitative research method they said that in qualitative research the researcher might interpret the behaviors of the participants which can lead to unreliable results.

Research Method

We used semi-structured interviews to get the original point of views or responses while collecting data for this research. Quinlan (2010) stated that this method helps the researcher explore the views and thoughts of the respondent's in the same context. This method is more like to normal conversation. For this research, this data collection technique seemed to be best as respondents open up and share their experiences in detail, challenges. Although, this technique is highly time-consuming, but gives a lot of useful data.

2.1 Strategic Objectives and their Relevance with Women's Advancement and Rights:

Fast modern development and improvement: A sound and safe workplace will be built up through fortifying the mechanical approach and legitimate structure. This, thus, is required to guarantee interest of ladies as specialists just as business people for modern generation and in this manner enable and further create them. Improved nature of Bangladesh items predictable with global measures: Half of the poor are ladies. Expanding acquiring force will enable ladies and upgrade their standardized savings and improve their financial conditions. Condition agreeable mechanical improvement: These exercises will diminish wellbeing dangers for ladies laborers. Subsequently it will guarantee great wellbeing for moms and their relatives. Mechanical development in high need parts: This will positively affect ladies occupied with farming exercises through access to reasonable compost inputs. Create Entrepreneurship and gifted work power: By guaranteeing ladies' interest in different preparing programs and through corresponding distributions of mechanical plots to ladies business people, the monetary and economic wellbeing of ladies will be improved. Business

age: Growth of little and bungalow ventures will improve open doors for work of ladies and this will engage ladies and improve their monetary conditions. Guaranteeing beneficial State-claimed ventures: Women laborers are a piece of the workforce of state-possessed undertakings and will subsequently profit by progressively productive managers.

2.2 Roles and Responsibilities of the Government for Women's Advancement and Rights:

1. To accomplish Vision-2021, by agreeing due significance to the hands-on preparing for ladies, the exercises of Bangladesh Industrial and Technical Assistance Center (BITAC) have been extended and to date, 4,436 ladies have been furnished with specialized preparing under the undertaking titled Extension of BITAC for Self-work and Destitution Alleviation through Hands on specialized preparing featuring Women. Of those, 1,824 ladies have become independent.
2. Business people who are eager to build up mechanical units in little, medium and cabin enterprises are being prepared by the Bangladesh Small and Cottage Industries Corporation (BSCIC). They are additionally being given low premium acknowledge, mechanical plots with created framework, help with promoting their items along with different motivations. From 2009-10 to 2013-14 (July-February), 42,188 individuals were prepared. Amid this period, 599 plots have been apportioned to business people.
3. BSCIC has been assuming a crucial job for advancement and advancement of little businesses in the private part. The undertakings which are being actualized by BSIC are relied upon to give work to around 200,000 ladies;
4. The task "Advancement of Bee-keeping through Modern Technology is being actualized by the BSCIC gone for preparing 2,000 honey bee managers in an advanced and logical strategies, of which 800 are ladies. After the fruition of preparing, one honey bee box will be given to each prepared ladies without expense alongside little credit.
5. The 1997-98 Vitamin A status overview surveyed that pre-younger students and pregnant ladies are at serious hazard of Vitamin An insufficiency particularly in town and urban ghetto regions. The UNICEF upheld venture titled Fortress of Edible Oil Bangladesh is being executed under this service. After culmination oil fortress programed, ladies of conceptive age, neonates and school-age kids will profit by the supplementation of Vitamin A.
6. To monetarily enable ladies, renegotiating worth 754.25 centers Taka for 9,612 ladies business people has been done which is 21.83 percent of the all out renegotiating sum. Banking/non-banking budgetary organizations may consider giving greatest 25 lakh Taka credit office against big business adventure related assets and insurance of associations/business people if the business person is a "lady modern business person" who is accepting credit from the renegotiating reserve; or, the dominant part proprietors of the credit beneficiary association are ladies. Enterprise advancement alludes to preparing and other help administrations consolidated inside an organized program intended to help people and gatherings keen on getting to be business visionaries and beginning little organizations. (Seed Working Paper No. 14, Series on ladies' Entrepreneurship Development and Gender in Ventures WEDGE, Jobs, Sender and Small Enterprises in Bangladesh: Factor Affecting Women Business visionaries in Small and Cottage Industries in Bangladesh by Nilufer Ahmed Karim) According to Nilufer Ahmed

Karim following are the deterrents to the development and improvement of ladies business enterprise:

1. National modern arrangement presently can't seem to perceive enterprise improvement as an industrialization methodology. When all is said in done, current strategy puts under accentuation on the setting up of endeavors instead of on business enterprise itself. The human factor has gotten least consideration in the advancement ventures.
2. Government strategy proclamations stress the job of ladies being developed exercises, however what are absent are well-structured projects to persuade ladies to enter enterprising exercises on a more noteworthy scale.
3. An excessive number of potential female business visionaries stay ignorant of government offices, backing and motivations
4. Since ladies are relative newcomers to business enterprise, they need exceptional consideration on the off chance that they are to build up a decent footing. Up until this point, no business enterprise improvement program, in the genuine feeling of the term, addresses the uncommon necessities of ladies.
5. As a result of their moderately low education rates, ladies by and large are less gifted than men as business person.
6. Customarily, ladies will in general go into general instruction rather than specialized, abilities arranged projects. Absence of specialized learning blocks ladies' entrance into innovatively refined exercises with potential for better efficiency and expanded gainfulness.
7. Ominous social practices and social restraints militate against the improvement of ladies business enterprise. For ladies, work outside the family is derided and debilitated.
8. Numerous ladies are vigorously associated with family unit and tyke bearing exercises, and subsequently they do not have the time to direct effective business exercises. little has been done to present different types of innovation that lessens the drudgery of family unit work.
9. Ladies have little access to either institutional or non-institutional credit offices for their fixed or working capital prerequisites. These frames of mind confine the entrance of autonomous female business people to credit.
10. The interest from the banks for insurance is another obstacle to getting the credit.
11. Muddled and extensive methodology and high exchange costs dishearten getting from banks.
12. High managerial and dealing with costs make business banks commonly hesitant to allow little credits to business visionaries.
13. Enthusiasm on bank credits ranges from 12 to 16 percent, while degrees of profitability earned by ladies are generally low. This additionally debilitates ladies from looking for credit from the banks.
13. Absence of access to improved innovation is a noteworthy requirement which blocked the efficiency successfully and effectively.
14. Item advertising has dependably been a significant issues now for sell the items. Without appropriate promoting plan it is extremely hard to place and sell the item.

3. Objectives of the Study

The objective of the study is, to make policy and institutional framework for developing entrepreneurial skills, providing vocation education and training has widened the horizon for economic empowerment of women. Thus, more specifically the study aims to explore:

- I. To identify significant policy implementation on how to improve women entrepreneurship development in Bangladesh
- II. The study attempts to recommend some policies to reduce the hindrance & to pave the way of their success.

4. Methodology of the Study

The study is based largely on secondary data from published sources including websites of different organizations. Data and information from secondary sources were collected by consulting various relevant journals, studies conducted by various donor and development agencies, and publications of Asian Development Bank, International Labor Organization, Bank of Small Industries and Commerce, Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics etc.

Figure 1. Trend of Women Entrepreneurship Development Of Bangladesh (From SMEF & MIDA 2009)

Women entrepreneur in 2015		
Name of Division (Number of Districts)	Number of Women Entrepreneur	Percent of Women Entrepreneur
Dhaka (17)	155	33.4
Chittagong (11)	81	17.1
Rangpur (8)	68	13.9
Rajshahi (8)	52	12.5
Khulna (10)	46	11.1
Sylhet (4)	31	7.5
Barisal (6)	19	4.6

Source: Field Survey, BB, 2015.

Disbursement of loan to women entrepreneur in 2010 and 2013				
GROUP OF BANKS	2010		2013	
	Male Amount	Female Amount	Male Amount	Female Amount
SoCBS	7320.39	203.59	5007.85	140.07
PCBS	39110.35	1384.22	70546.41	2865.48
SPBS	2589.57	105.09	3522.31	168.05
FCBS	1074.37	59.56	1145.04	42.00
TOTAL	50094.68	1752.46	80221.61	3215.60

Note: 1 crore = 10 million Source, SME & Special Programmes Department, BB.

Table 1. Distribution of Ownership By Gender Of Owner Within Smes

Particulars	Percent of all SMEs	Average no. of workers	Percent of SME employment
Women	6	2.3	2
Men	94	15.5	96
Co-ownership by men	1	7.6	1
Total	100	5.2	100

Source: Daniels (2003)

Table 2. Sector-Wise Business Participation By Women Entrepreneur

Sector	% of Enterprise
Handicraft	72
Garment	9
Parlor	8
Food	3
Agro based	3
Printing	1
ICT	2
Others	2
Total (n=50)	100

Conclusion and Policy Recommendations

Entrepreneurship is the key to the creation of new enterprises that energize and revitalize the economy. Entrepreneurship serves as the catalyst in the process of industrialization and economic growth. Women entrepreneurs can play a vital role in combating rural poverty. The emergence and development of women entrepreneurship largely depends on the supporting conditions of different factors such as economic, social, cultural, and psychological. To improve the socio-economic status of the women in Bangladesh it is necessary to formulate appropriate policies, take necessary actions and introduce effective measures to integrate the women in the mainstream of the development process. Therefore, the following recommendations may be considered worthwhile:

(i) Financial Policies and Strategies: In respect of the policy, strategy and function of Bangladesh Bank and Commercial Banks following recommendations may be made:

- Identification of viable women entrepreneurs.
- Establishing credit guarantee scheme for women entrepreneurs.
- Sinking interest rate for loans for women entrepreneurs.
- Setting up special window for financing women entrepreneurs.
- Pre- and post investment counseling for women entrepreneurs for credit.
- Allocation of women share in equity development and fund.
- Preferential treatment of the women entrepreneurs by credit in thrust sectors.
- Monitoring of credit disbursement for women entrepreneurs.

- Maintaining gender based data on credit disbursement and dissemination information on credit opportunities.
 - One stop service should be created in the Commerce Ministry exclusively for the women entrepreneurs for facilitating investment and business
 - Establishing a women bank.
 - Enabling credit for the women without collateral.
- (ii) Counselling and support services: There are following counseling and support services to facilitate women entrepreneurship in Bangladesh: • Credit programs need to be linked with entrepreneurship development training programs. • Lending procedures must be simplified, with minimum documentation formalities. • Special provisions should be made for female entrepreneurs.
- (iii) Other Suggestions: There are following other recommendations for facilitating women entrepreneurship:
- Tax holiday for women entrepreneurs should extended further and made more supportive for them.
 - Gift Tax should be dismantled in the case of women beneficiaries.
 - Either the registration procedure for import and export business should be simplified and made women friendly or completely dismantled.
 - All anomalies in custom procedure must be removed and women friendly.
 - Tariff for women entrepreneurs should be abolished.
 - Value Added Tax (VAT) for women entrepreneurs should be abolished. Therefore, Government and private sector interventions have generally accelerated income generating activities of women both in the urban and rural areas with entrepreneurship development. Such kind of support services, policies, and strategies help to change the scenario of Bangladesh especially for the women who have gathered courage to break barriers and enter the off-house working force as entrepreneurs and workers - a situation not appropriate for women or accepted by the society in the past.

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